

RakshakAI: Multi-Label Toxicity Detection for Low-Resource Nepali Social Media Content

Biraj Bhusal

Independent Researcher

Kathmandu, Nepal

bhusalbiraj8@gmail.com

Abstract

We present **RakshakAI**, an early multi-label toxicity detection system and dataset for Nepali social media content moderation. Nepali, spoken by over 30 million people, remains underrepresented in natural language processing research, with very limited publicly available resources for toxicity detection. To explore this problem, we build a dataset of 1,574 samples spanning five toxicity categories: hate speech, casteism, religious incitement, political defamation, and cyberbullying. The dataset combines manually collected Facebook and YouTube comments with synthetically generated samples and back-translation augmentation, resulting in a final training corpus of 4,716 samples. We fine-tune a two-stage pipeline using LoRA/PEFT: a multi-label classifier for toxicity detection, followed by a severity classifier that uses both the original text and detected labels to predict three levels of content severity. We also evaluate LLaMA 3.3 70B in a zero-shot prompting setup as a baseline for contextual toxicity detection. The system is deployed as a live demo for experimentation and future improvement. We release the dataset, models, and system to support continued work in low-resource Nepali NLP.

Content Warning: This paper contains examples of toxic, offensive, and abusive language in Nepali for research purposes. The authors do not endorse any of the views expressed in the dataset examples.

1 Introduction

Social media platforms have become primary spaces for public discourse in Nepal, with millions of users engaging daily on Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok. However, these platforms have also become breeding grounds for toxic content including hate

speech targeting ethnic minorities, caste-based discrimination, religious incitement, political defamation, and cyberbullying. Despite the widespread use of social media in Nepal, there are very few automated moderation tools designed for Nepali content.

The Nepali language presents unique challenges for natural language processing. It is written in Devanagari script but commonly appears in Romanized form and code-mixed with English on social media. Existing multilingual toxicity detection systems trained primarily on high-resource languages such as English demonstrate limited effectiveness on Nepali due to significant linguistic and cultural differences.

In this paper, we make the following contributions:

- We release a multi-label Nepali toxicity dataset covering five toxicity categories commonly observed on social media.
- We fine-tune XLM-RoBERTa Large using LoRA/PEFT on this dataset, achieving strong multi-label classification performance.
- We also evaluate LLaMA 3.3 70B in a zero-shot setting to explore how large language models perform on Nepali toxicity detection without task-specific training.
- We deploy both models in a live, publicly accessible content moderation system at <https://huggingface.co/spaces/biraj-bhusal/rakshak-ai>.
- We release our dataset and models publicly to support future research.

2 Background: Nepali Language and Social Media

2.1 The Nepali Language and Social Media Context

Nepali is the official language of Nepal, spoken by over 30 million people worldwide. While predominantly used in Nepal, significant Nepali-speaking communities exist in India and across the global diaspora. It is written in Devanagari script, the same script used by Hindi and Sanskrit.

What makes Nepali social media content particularly challenging for automated moderation is the extreme variation in how the language is written online. Users commonly write in at least three distinct forms:

- **Devanagari Nepali** — the standard written form using Devanagari script, e.g., “यो देश बर्बाद भयो” (This country is ruined)
- **Romanized Nepali** — Nepali words written using Latin characters, e.g., “*yo desh barbad bhayo*” — the same sentence written phonetically in English letters. This form is extremely common among younger users and on platforms like Facebook and YouTube.
- **Code-mixed Nepali-English** — a blend of Nepali and English within the same sentence, e.g., “*Bro yo politician totally useless छ*” (Bro this politician is totally useless), where छ (cha) is a Nepali auxiliary verb meaning “is”. Another example: “यो *sarkar le k gardai xa thaha छैन*” (I don’t know what this government is doing)

This variation reflects generational and platform differences — younger users tend to write in Romanized or code-mixed form, while older users more commonly use Devanagari. A single toxic post may combine all three forms.

Nepali social media also contains highly context-dependent language. For example, *maar* literally means “kill” but is commonly used as slang for “awesome” (e.g., “*ekdam maar game*” means “absolutely awesome game”). Similarly, caste and ethnic group names such as *Madhesi*, *Dalit*, and *Bahun* can appear in neutral or deeply derogatory

contexts depending on framing — making keyword-based detection fundamentally unreliable.

Despite having over 30 million speakers, Nepali remains severely underrepresented in NLP research due to limited commercial incentive, a scarcity of labeled datasets, and the complexity of processing informal social media text across multiple scripts. To help address the lack of Nepali NLP resources, we release a toxicity dataset together with trained models and a publicly accessible demo system.

3 Related Work

3.1 Toxicity Detection in High-Resource Languages

Toxicity and hate speech detection has been extensively studied for high-resource languages, particularly English. Davidson et al. (2017) introduced one of the earliest hate speech datasets for English Twitter. Transformer-based models such as BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) and RoBERTa have since become standard approaches, achieving strong performance across multiple benchmarks.

3.2 NLP Research for Nepali

Nepali remains one of the least studied languages in NLP research despite having over 30 million speakers worldwide. While some progress has been made in recent years, the availability of labeled datasets for Nepali NLP tasks remains severely limited compared to high-resource languages.

Sitoula et al. (2025) propose a hybrid model combining XLM-RoBERTa with convolutional modules for Nepali sentiment analysis, achieving up to 79.52% accuracy across multiple datasets. While demonstrating the effectiveness of multilingual models for Nepali text, sentiment analysis differs fundamentally from toxicity detection in scope and label granularity.

Singh et al. (2020) present a dataset for aspect-based abusive sentiment analysis in Nepali social media using code-mixed YouTube comments — one of the few prior efforts on Nepali abusive language. However, these works focus on sentiment classification and do not address the broader toxicity categories specific to the Nepali socio-political con-

text.

Timilsina (2020) explore offensive language detection in Nepali social media; however, their dataset is composed entirely in Devanagari script, limiting applicability to the large portion of users — particularly younger demographics — who write in Romanized Nepali or code-mixed Nepali-English. Our dataset explicitly addresses this gap by including text across all three forms: Devanagari, Romanized, and code-mixed.

Despite these efforts, no prior work has introduced a labeled dataset specifically addressing multi-label toxicity detection covering hate speech, casteism, religious incitement, political defamation, and cyberbullying simultaneously in Nepali. To the best of our knowledge, this work represents the first such contribution for the Nepali language.

3.3 Multilingual Toxicity Detection

Multilingual models such as mBERT and XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2020) have enabled cross-lingual transfer for low-resource languages. Recent work has explored hate speech detection across multiple languages simultaneously. However, Nepali is rarely included in such efforts because of the limited availability of labeled datasets.

4 Dataset

4.1 Data Collection

Our dataset was collected and curated in three stages, resulting in a final training set of 4,716 samples. First, 184 samples were manually collected from Facebook (75%) and YouTube (25%) comment sections covering news, politics, and social topics. These samples were manually labeled by the author and serve as the most reliable portion of the dataset. Second, approximately 1,400 additional samples were synthetically generated using large language models (ChatGPT and Gemini), using the 184 gold-standard samples as reference examples to ensure realistic and consistent labeling. After combining the collected and synthetic examples, the dataset contained 1,574 samples. Third, the full dataset was expanded through back-translation augmentation via English and Hindi as intermediate languages, producing natural paraphrases of each

sample while preserving original labels, yielding a final training corpus of 4,716 samples. The curated dataset (1,574 samples) and the augmented training dataset (4,716 samples) are both released publicly.¹

4.2 Label Schema

Each sample is annotated with five binary toxicity labels and a severity score. The five categories are defined as follows:

- **Hate Speech** — dehumanizing language, slurs, or calls targeting a group based on identity
- **Casteism** — caste-based discrimination, slurs, or untouchability references
- **Religious Incitement** — content attacking a religion or inciting violence against religious groups
- **Political Defamation** — false accusations or defamatory content targeting political figures
- **Cyberbullying** — personal attacks, threats, or harassment targeting specific individuals

Severity is annotated on a scale of 1–5, where 1 indicates completely clean content and 5 indicates extreme violence or explicit threats. Labels are not mutually exclusive; a single post may simultaneously trigger multiple categories. For model training, the five severity levels are mapped to three classes: normal (scores 1–2), moderate (score 3), and severe (scores 4–5).

4.3 Dataset Statistics

The overall composition and category distributions of the dataset are analyzed below. Specific examples are also presented to illustrate how each toxicity label is applied.

¹Curated dataset (1,574 samples): <https://huggingface.co/datasets/biraj-bhusal/rakshak-all-data-combined>
Augmented training dataset (4,716 samples): <https://huggingface.co/datasets/biraj-bhusal/rakshak-nepali-toxicity-final>

Text	HS	CA	RI	PD	CB	Sev
आज साथीहरूसँग पोखरा जाने टिकट काटियो (Bought tickets to Pokhara with friends today)	0	0	0	0	0	1
yo jaat ko manchhe haru lai nepal bata nikala (Expel people of this caste from Nepal)	1	1	0	0	0	5
BREAKING: PM le desh bechxa, share garnus!! (BREAKING: PM is selling the country, share this!!)	0	0	0	1	0	4
tero photo viral gardinchu chupchaap bas (I will make your photo viral, stay quiet)	0	0	0	0	1	4

Table 1: Example samples from the dataset. Severity is on the raw 1–5 scale, HS=Hate Speech, CA=Casteism, RI=Religious Incitement, PD=Political Defamation, CB=Cyberbullying, Sev=Severity (raw 1–5 scale; mapped to 3 classes for model training).

Category	Count	%
Hate Speech	1,427	30.3%
Casteism	507	10.7%
Religious Incitement	417	8.8%
Political Defamation	810	17.2%
Cyberbullying	1,137	24.1%
Clean	1,699	36.0%

Table 2: Dataset label distribution. Percentages sum to more than 100% due to multi-label annotations.

Figure 1: Distribution of toxicity labels across the dataset. A sample may carry multiple labels simultaneously.

4.4 Text Characteristics

The dataset contains text in three script formats: pure Devanagari, Romanized Nepali, and code-mixed Nepali-English. Posts range from short 3–5 word comments to multi-sentence rants, reflecting realistic social media behavior. The dataset intentionally includes Nepali slang, abbreviations, typos, hashtags, and mentions as found in real social media content.

5 Methodology

5.1 Fine-tuned XLM-RoBERTa

We fine-tune XLM-RoBERTa Large (Conneau et al., 2020) for multi-label sequence classification using parameter-efficient fine-tuning via LoRA (Hu et al., 2022) with rank $r = 16$, $\alpha = 32$, and dropout of 0.1 applied to query and value projection matrices. The model is trained for 15 epochs with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , batch size of 8 with gradient accumulation steps of 4 (effective batch size 32), and a warmup ratio of 0.1. Mixed precision (fp16) training is used throughout. A sigmoid activa-

tion with threshold 0.5 is applied to logits for multi-label prediction. All experiments were conducted on Kaggle with dual NVIDIA T4 GPUs using mixed precision (fp16) training.

5.2 LLaMA 3.3 70B Prompted Baseline

We evaluate LLaMA 3.3 70B (Touvron et al., 2023) in a zero-shot setting via structured prompting. The prompt includes detailed label definitions, Nepal-specific cultural context (ethnic group names, common slang, threat vocabulary), and strict output formatting as a JSON object. Temperature is set to 0.1 for near-deterministic outputs. Since the model is used in a zero-shot setting, no additional training is required.

5.3 Severity Prediction

A separate severity classifier is trained on the augmented dataset to predict a three-class severity label: normal (original scores

1–2), moderate (score 3), and severe (scores 4–5). Rather than predicting severity from text alone, the classifier input is enriched by appending the detected toxicity labels from the multi-label classifier to the original text (e.g., [DETECTED: hate_speech, casteism]), allowing the model to leverage category information when estimating severity. The classifier uses the same XLM-RoBERTa Large backbone with LoRA fine-tuning. Class-weighted cross-entropy loss is used to address class imbalance, with the minority moderate class upweighted accordingly.

6 Experiments and Results

6.1 Multi-Label Classification

Model	F1 Macro	F1 Micro
XLM-RoBERTa Large	0.846	0.833

Table 3: Multi-label classification results on test set.

XLM-RoBERTa Large achieves an F1 macro score of 0.846 and F1 micro of 0.833 on the held-out test set, indicating effective performance on multi-label toxicity classification for Nepali social media text. LLaMA 3.3 70B was evaluated qualitatively through deployment testing; formal benchmarking was not conducted due to API cost constraints and is left for future work.

Figure 2: XLM-RoBERTa Large training progress over 15 epochs on the Nepali toxicity dataset.

6.2 Severity Classification

The severity model performs strongly on the normal and severe classes but struggles with moderate severity, primarily due to class imbalance — only 439 of 4,716 training samples

Class	Precision	Recall	F1
Normal (1–2)	0.94	0.87	0.90
Moderate (3)	0.25	0.27	0.26
Severe (4–5)	0.86	0.91	0.88

Table 4: Severity classification results (3-class).

(9.3%) carry a moderate severity label. This is likely because moderate toxicity is harder to define consistently than clearly safe or clearly harmful content., where the boundary between mild and clearly harmful content is often ambiguous, and remains a known challenge in severity annotation tasks.

7 Deployment

RakshakAI is deployed as a publicly accessible web application built with Gradio and hosted on HuggingFace Spaces.² The system provides two independent analysis tabs — one powered by LLaMA 3.3 70B and one by the fine-tuned XLM-RoBERTa model — allowing users to compare outputs across both approaches. All predictions are logged anonymously and will be periodically reviewed, filtered for quality, and added to the training dataset to improve model accuracy over time. The system accepts input in Devanagari, Romanized Nepali, and code-mixed text.

8 Limitations

Several limitations of this work should be acknowledged. First, the gold-standard portion of the dataset contains only 184 manually labeled samples, with the remainder synthetically generated. Although synthetic examples help increase dataset size, they may not capture the full variety of toxicity found on real social media platforms. Second, all manual annotations were performed by a single annotator, which limits inter-annotator agreement analysis and may introduce individual labeling bias. Third, the severity model performs poorly on the moderate class (F1 = 0.26) due to its underrepresentation in the dataset, a limitation we plan to address through continued data collection. Fourth, LLaMA 3.3 70B is evaluated

²Live system: <https://huggingface.co/spaces/biraj-bhusal/rakshak-ai>
Label Model: <https://huggingface.co/biraj-bhusal/rakshak-xlmr-large-v2>
Severity Model: <https://huggingface.co/biraj-bhusal/rakshak-severity-v2>

only qualitatively through deployment observations, as formal benchmarking was not feasible due to API cost constraints — a rigorous quantitative comparison between the two approaches is left for future work.

9 Conclusion

We present RakshakAI as an early multi-label toxicity detection dataset and system for Nepali social media. Our fine-tuned XLM-RoBERTa Large model achieves an F1 macro of 0.846 across five toxicity categories, and our two-stage pipeline also predicts content severity through a dedicated severity classifier. The deployed system can collect additional examples that may help improve future versions of the model. We release the dataset, models, and code publicly to support further work on automated content moderation for low-resource languages. Future work will focus on expanding the manually labeled dataset, improving moderate severity prediction, collecting more annotator labels to reduce individual bias, and formally evaluating LLaMA as a baseline.

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